

Clinical and nonclinical statistics roles in the pharmaceutical industry: How knowledge of one helps the other

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Abstract

A career development session, sponsored by the Career Development committee of the Biopharmaceutical Section of the ASA, was held on Tuesday August 8, 2023, at the Joint Statistical Meetings, in Toronto. The session was organized by Stan Altan (Janssen), Scott Clark (Eli Lilly) and John Kolassa (Rutgers University), with the following senior leaders of statistics departments in the pharmaceutical industry serving as panelists: Imola Fodor (Genentech), Cyrus Hoseyni (Janssen), Eve Pickering (Pfizer), and Shanthi Sethuraman (Eli Lilly). The session was targeted to clinical and nonclinical statisticians in the pharmaceutical industry, especially those early in their career. The panel members spoke to the advantages of career development benefitting from knowledge and experience from both development spaces. Eight prepared questions and four audience questions were discussed.

Keywords: career development, nonclinical statistics, clinical statistics, patient-centric specifications

1. Introduction

Session chair, Scott Clark, began by introducing the main topics for discussion, highlighting the need for a closer linkage between the clinical and nonclinical spaces. This is occurring as “patient centric specifications” considerations in the nonclinical space intersects with “Patient-focused drug development (PFDD)” in the clinical space. Translational medicine has traditionally been at the juncture of nonclinical and clinical pursuits. But more recently, scientific and regulatory developments have motivated companies to study product quality attributes with clinical relevance considerations in mind. This convergence is expected to expand into the future. Given this convergence, the question was raised as to how career development benefits from knowledge and experience across the two areas.

As further background for the relevance of the session topics, the subject matter spheres pertinent to the clinical and nonclinical areas were reviewed (see Appendix 2, Figures 1 and 2). The following two aspects of the current technological landscape having potential to dramatically impact on statisticians in the pharmaceutical industry were highlighted.

1. The continuing emphasis on patient-focused drug development in clinical studies and the parallel development of patient centric specifications in the nonclinical space. These initiatives imply a need for greater collaborations between the clinical and

nonclinical spaces moving forward. Specifically Figure 3 shows graphically the organic linkages between manufacturing process, the pharmaceutical product and the patient outcomes, and product quality.

2. Rapidly evolving technologies and science driving drug development is another important driver of the expected convergence. Closer collaborations are expected to accelerate the integration of these technological advances into the drug development process (see Appendix 2, Figure 4).

Setting the stage for further discussions, another question was posed “Are nonclinical to clinical connections ready for the coming revolution?” with the goal of illustrating the advantages of acquiring a basic understanding of the role of nonclinical statistics to the clinical statistician, and the reverse, advantages to acquiring a basic understanding of the role of clinical statistics to the nonclinical statistician. In the discussions, one important goal was to address the question of how this helps career development. Ideas on how to bridge any gaps in the connections is also sought. What are the connections points, what needs to be improved, and how does product quality impact on clinical outcomes?

2. Panelists’ opening statements.

Scott Clark introduced each of the panelists, followed by the panel discussion led by John Kolassa. It kicked off with opening statements by each of the panelists. The panelists gave a brief perspective on the main topic of the session. These are summarized as follows.

Imola Fodor (Vice President Data and Statistical Sciences, Hematology and Early Development, Genentech)

My professional journey started in nonclinical statistics for 10 years, and then I moved to clinical. I very much appreciate the diversity of statistical tools and approaches used across the drug development process, and the impact that statisticians can have on the business. Having that experience in early development and nonclinical statistics was a major advantage to appreciate better the compound’s late development challenges.

Cyrus Hoseyni (Global Head, Statistics and Decision Sciences, Janssen)

The first 3 years post-graduation I spent supporting early development, toxicology, and in parallel, late development. Observing up close the end to end process provided me with valuable experience to help connect the parts of the entire process of drug development. This was not serendipitous; it was helped by having a sense of curiosity and seeking opportunities to learn and engage. Leaving such opportunities to chance is not sufficient, a proactive attitude, being ready to help, is essential to learning and growing.

Eve Pickering (Vice President, Nonclinical Statistics, Pfizer)

I had an undergraduate degree in physics, spending time in a lab generating scientific data. I moved to Statistics at Rutgers. Although it was a theoretical department, I gained practical experience supporting agricultural experiments. I moved to Wright State, was on the consulting center and the IACUC committee, supporting animal protocols. Then I moved to Pfizer. I was initially involved in a late development project. An early experience with the statistical issues of a biomarker and its analytical performance motivated me to return to the lab and nonclinical studies. All the work in early development feeds into later development stages, and knowing how the data is used in clinical development, helped inform my work in nonclinical.

Shanthi Sethuramen (R&D Global Analytics Officer and Sr. Vice President, Eli Lilly)

In my experience, taking short term assignments, getting outside your comfort zone and spending time in both non-clinical and clinical areas is the best way to learn and to see the bigger picture of the discovery, drug development process and post launch. Getting experience from outside of Statistics also has benefits. When I was part of project management, it allowed me to look at a molecule from birth to late stage. I gained a deeper insight into what it takes to make the molecule a product, and to optimize it later. Having an appreciation for the lifecycle of the molecule helps me to be a better critical thinker, understanding the importance of sharing knowledge across the silos and be a better drug developer. It's very importance to learn from one another and other functions.

3. Prepared discussion questions

John Kolassa moderated the discussions and posed questions to the panelists. This was intended to be a wide- ranging discussion on a set of questions directed to the panelists. The following are the series of questions and salient points made in response to the questions (4 questions which were not discussed due to a lack of time are given in Appendix 1.).

1. What are the important connections between early development/Discovery and implications on clinical studies?
 - a. From the perspective of safety, understanding toxicology data and its role in setting the “no regrets” human dose is important, especially with new modalities., and having a basic understanding of the PK/PD profile and pharmacology, mechanistic modeling helps with implications on clinical measures and outcomes.
 - b. There is a flow from discovery to the clinic, but there is also a flow back. For example, understanding immunogenicity issues in the clinic can feed back to the design of molecules in early nonclinical development, with the goal of minimizing toxicity issues in clinical trials.
 - c. We have huge databases of molecules with known physical and chemical properties, with possibly thousands of attributes. When seeking the one(s) that meets certain requirements for safety and efficacy, knowing the clinical implications informs the search for the right compound. While bioinformatics plays an important part, statistical models/methodologies help with potential multiplicity issues during the analyses and plays a significant role in the design of the molecules.
2. How do we contrast the diversity of statistical applications in nonclinical vs clinical and how does this impact on career trajectories?
 - a. The beauty of nonclinical and clinical statistics is that there are so many interesting questions requiring statistical approaches. Being less regulated in some cases in nonclinical, there is more flexibility in statistical approaches and innovative models. The nature of the variety of challenging problems in areas of nonclinical allow more creative and interesting statistical approaches. Experience with diverse statistical tools is important no matter which direction a statistician takes.
 - b. In clinical, patient safety is paramount. However, there is plenty of room on the clinical side to develop clinical development plans (CDPs). This is not a typical statistical question, but using our training in statistics and quantitative skills can help to inform the writing of the CDPs. This is a basic skill important to career development.

- c. The ratio of statisticians to scientists in nonclinical might be 1:400, so the duration of projects is shorter, and multiple projects in parallel is the norm. Therefore, project management becomes important. This is a skill that can be taken forward into the clinical side, a learning from non-clinical.
3. What is the potential and current role of AI (artificial intelligence) and ML (machine learning) in the clinical and nonclinical spaces?
 - a. AI and ML are best applied in the hands of experts who exercise a balance between augmentation and automation. Some caution is needed in placing such tools into the hands of novices, especially in the application of off the shelf applications. The statistician's role in helping understand the appropriate methodologies, modeling and statistical issues such as multiplicity are critical to getting to the right hypotheses and solutions.
 - b. AI can play a large role in the image analysis in cancer studies, and in augmenting pathology studies.
 - c. Machine learning opens up opportunities for deeper collaborations with data science colleagues and related approaches.
4. What kind of academic training can prepare statisticians to pursue clinical or nonclinical statistics roles in the industry. Would some kind of continuing education courses or certification mitigate lack of preparedness for an industry career.?
 - a. Having direct hands-on experience generating and handling data, translates to more effective understanding of data collection and generation by our collaborators. Taking classes in biology or chemistry can help to provide the language of our scientific collaborators, to enhance communication.
 - b. A statistics degree is not sufficient; interdisciplinary, or additional training in the sciences relevant to drug development makes you a better drug developer. Knowing the scientific language enhances collaboration.
 - c. Academic programs could consider internship programs, or having visiting lectures from industry statisticians to bring to students the experiences of statisticians on the job as one way to ameliorate the lack of awareness, for example different aspects of the drug development process. We should look for ways to collaborate more between industry and academia to address this.
5. What is the practice for making sure that nonclinical data are summarized and presented accurately?
 - a. Statisticians should approach this not as policemen of the process, but by asking what the goal is, are there biases in the data, making objective data-based decisions.
 - b. Present data and communicate findings clearly.
 - c. Education should be part of the role. Due diligence requires looking at the totality of the data, how we come into the process, and sharing the common goal of making the right decision based on the data. We must draw valid conclusions based on the data.
6. How can the statistical stakeholders add clarity to the dialogue? What Collaborations are desirable?

- a. Stakeholders may include both internal partners, e.g., clinical statistics, biomarker groups, PK/Pharmacology/Pharmacometrics, commercial supply chain; external partners, IQ consortium, DIA, AAPS, academic institutions, regulatory agencies.
 - b. Understanding the key factors that could influence the outcome, and understanding the underlying assumptions, informs the proper design of experiments, statistical analysis and modeling.
 - c. Expand your network across the industry, with regulators, scientific colleagues, not just statisticians. Consider working on industry working groups, especially those that are comprised of different disciplines, different companies, universities, all working on a research effort together. This experience will provide greater understanding of the big picture, and enhance innovation and the ability to work more effectively.
7. Can we incorporate QbD (quality by design) principles as a background for pursuing a patient centric specification? What are the hurdles?
- a. Linking quality attributes to clinical outcomes is an important goal. QbD is fundamentally defining an operating space, whether it's manufacturing, pKpD, or clinical. In manufacturing the goal is to justify expansion of the operating space, but in clinical, it is the opposite, product variability in clinical trials is reduced. This basic conflict needs some resolution, but finding an approach efficiently, is still a challenge.
 - b. The question of how CMC (Chemistry, Manufacturing and Control) attributes relate to ADME (Absorption Distribution Metabolism Excretion) properties is an important question, the concept is appealing but can this question be brought into the clinic using DoE (design of experiments), subject to time and cost constraints? This is still a challenge.
 - c. This is an emerging topic that will require deeper engagement by statisticians. We must embrace the technological advances, and in the process, this may open new possibilities for this to be studied in an efficient way.
8. Do you agree that patient value is enhanced by clinical statisticians recognizing the purpose of pharmaceutical product quality, nonclinical statisticians recognizing connections of product quality attributes with clinical endpoints?
- a. Having experience in both areas helps us see the bigger picture.
 - b. Understanding the business, what are the important questions, and why these questions are important, allows statisticians to play a more influential role. Experience in both areas enables a broader perspective and allows for a better appreciation for the relevant questions of drug development.
 - c. People can pigeonhole statisticians, but seeing the end to end picture and demonstrating your knowledge of the early development data, the toxicology data, the acquisition data, when you talk like a drug developer, the attitude changes. So, it is important to have business acumen and see the whole process end to end. This has large dividends.

4. Audience questions

1. How can statisticians hired into one area acquire experience in the entire end to end drug development process?

- a. The most important factor is the awareness of the importance of getting this kind of experience. Some organizations have rotation options, but the individual statistician can work with their management and ask to put it into their development plan.
 - b. “Challenge” or “Stretch” assignments may be an option at some companies to work on short term projects in other areas. Be proactive in finding multiple assignments that bring you new opportunities, possibly outside your comfort zone, to learn and grow. Be curious.
 - c. Senior Managers frequently encourage their staff to get experience on both sides. If your management does not support your interest in doing this, it might be a good time to seek other opportunities.
2. I am an isolated statistician, lacking a PhD, working for a smaller organization, with no or few statistical colleagues, with a heavy workload. I find balancing statistical rigor with business needs a challenge. How can someone in this position handle this?
- a. Being a one person department means you have to make more of an effort to demonstrate your value to the organization. Look for opportunities to get more deeply engaged. It can be simple, maybe a data presentation strategy, how to help your colleagues make their case in the best way. Start with smaller opportunities to show your value to the organization.
 - b. Being alone, the primary goal should be to avoid wrong interpretations of the data that could lead to incorrect decisions. Framing the data, the interpretation and risks such that a data supported decision strategy can be established should be the critical objective.
 - c. Understand what the decision maker’s priorities are, see things from their side, discuss their thoughts and let them speak more. This can lead to good negotiation to get to a satisfactory decision.
3. How can we foster more collaboration between clinical and nonclinical at our companies?
- a. Statisticians speak the same language, so the statisticians can often be the conduit to enhance and build bridges between different stakeholders. Breaking down the silos will naturally lead to more collaboration.
 - b. Leverage your experience and knowledge, and look for opportunities to share that knowledge across the areas.
 - c. Have conversations about the molecule, know the animal data, and help to inform the downstream clinical implications.
 - d. The more each group knows about the other, the better they can appreciate their technical issues. This may not happen organically, so some effort has to be made. Pharmacology/Pharmacometrics groups can be a good start for this kind of communication and knowledge sharing.
4. Collaborators sometimes ask that statistical results to be reduced down to a single number. But when a spectrum of results is the necessary interpretation, how do we bridge this tension between complexity and the demand for a simple answer.
- a. This is where the job of the statistician to walk the collaborator to a decision is extremely important. Walk through the background to the research problem and

the data collected to address the problem. Approach it as first providing the bottom line, and then follow up with how you got there. Then discuss concerns and caveats.

- b. Communicating the topline result is an art, but necessary when communicating to decision makers. Takes practice. See it as an opportunity and challenge to make the right decision.
- c. You're facilitating the decision; you're not making the decision. There should be a back and forth, ask what you think this means. The collaborator must have a sense of the data as well, what is their conclusion. Get their perspective. Help them make the decision you want.

5. Discussion on Opportunities to apply "soft skills"

- a. As applied scientists, soft skills related to influence, collaboration, and engagement will further the statistician's effectiveness. Tukey said, "We play in everybody's back yard", so these soft skills are essential. Curiosity and showing interest in the collaborator's research questions is important. It's also important to avoid a skeptical attitude and to approach communications from the perspective of trying to understand.
- b. The goal is making the right decisions, using the right data, the right design, paying attention to bias and sources of variability. This ability makes the statistician's role extremely valuable and allows statisticians to engage in preparation for internal and external (regulatory) questions and dialogue.
- c. Our collaborators want to do good science, our role is to help them pursue the science as partners and to enable the right decisions. It's important to remember to be helpful, think about consequences, be tactful, unbiased, and calm under fire. This is very much a fine art, honed by those who are successful in the business.

6. Final remarks

John Kolassa ended the session with thanks to the panelists and the audience of 51 people, with "We play in everyone's back yard, but remember, it's not our back yard. We have to understand it's their back yard, so we have to be diplomatic in how we negotiate what happens in their back yard".

7. References

1. S. Altan, T. Schofield, D. LeBlond (2023). A Framework to Achieving Quality in Pharmaceutical Therapeutics and Vaccine Development. Biopharmaceutical Report, Vol.30, No, 1 Spring 2023 <https://community.amstat.org/biop/biopharmreport>

8. Acknowledgements

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Appendix 1 – Prepared questions not discussed due to time limitation

1. Beyond effective designs, what are key learnings across the nonclinical/clinical spectrum that you have seen impact statistical innovation?
2. How does domain knowledge or business acumen that you learned across roles affect your ability to influence business partners and/or company leaders?
3. The explosion of available data from genomics, imaging, single-cell RNA, etc. present new challenges to statisticians and data scientists but differing skills necessary in the clinical vs nonclinical roles. How should statisticians best prepare for the fast-changing science and data explosion?
4. In thinking of insights and productivity between nonclinical and clinical roles, how might these be impacted by the expansion of artificial intelligence and machine learning tools?

Appendix 2 – Referenced figures

Figure 1 Statistics Spheres in Drug Development

Figure 2 Comparison of objectives clinical vs nonclinical statistics

Nonclinical Spheres

Drug discovery

- Identifying a new, potentially important therapeutic compound
- MOA and downstream actions
- Fine tuning the molecule so it works as a drug

Preclinical

- Avoid anti-drug reactions in humans
- Translating the animal experiments into something salient in humans

CM&C (Target Product Profile)

- Analytical Tools
- Formulation into a shelf stable and bioavailable dosage form
- Manufacturing process scale to commercial size
- Life cycle management
- Product quality specifications

Clinical Sphere

Establish safety and efficacy of the drug product

- **Phase 0**
 - Interface with Translational Medicine studies
 - Implications of animal studies
- **Phase 1**
 - Safety and pK/pD through crossover studies
- **Phase 2**
 - Dose ranging studies
- **Phase 3 (Efficacy and Safety)**
 - Parallel vs Adaptive designs
- **Phase 4**
 - Post marketing, RWE

Figure 3 Patient-focused Drug Development in clinical studies, Patient-centric in nonclinical studies and statistical opportunities for closer collaborations

Product-Process-Patient Linkages and Quality Expectations under Patient Centric Drug Development

Figure 4 Evolving science impacting drug discovery and development.

Sources: Evaluate Pharma; BCG analysis.

^aNot including products that are inactive or have been withdrawn from market as of October 2022.

Source: <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2023/benefits-and-risks-of-new-drug-modalities>